

Sustainable Approach to City Development: A Case of Kullu Valley, Himachal Pradesh, India

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Abstract

The sustainable cities in and around the world today account for different types of sustainability. The case taken up for research is located in the Lower Himalayan region of the Indian sub-continent. The Kullu valley is the most urbanized area in the Upper Beas Region which the largest basin of the Himalayan range in India and caters almost 7 lakhs population in the region. The kullu valley is not only known for its rich cultural heritage but also very rich in its ecological resource. The author has tried to conduct on-site surveys and analysed the type of sustainability methods adopted by the local people of the Kullu valley. This helped in understanding the various types of methodologies and approaches that can be adopted for critical areas of interventions. The major focus area was identified on the basis of the study analysis on the basis of maps generated out of site visit and secondary studies on the region.

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1. Introduction

The Kullu town and its surrounding areas that form the Kullu valley is a rich ecological resource of the region. It is composed of landforms that range from 1200m to 4400m in elevation. It covers grasslands, built typologies, forest covers, barren lands, scrub lands, agricultural fields, horticulture lands and distant snow fed mountains. All of these form an important resource and it is important to maintain its equity for a sustainable development of the region. The author has tried to frame out how the definition of sustainability may differ for similar locations as the Kullu valley. The author has also tried to understand the various natural cycles and systems that are taking place in the region and how it can be a useful tool

for not only a sustainable region but also a resilient region in the entire Himalayan center. The author has made an attempt to brief about a pilot project taken up for the region where the major concentration is on an indigenous method for the development of the watershed in the Kullu valley sub-shed.

2. Land

Land is a very important resource, especially in a country like India where the population growth is at its peak ever since independence. The importance of land is well understood and managed in this entire region. The author has tried to map the important geological and physiococial features in the region along with the different timelines of land use and land cover changes that brief about the basis of the analytical theories of the research.

1-2- Geology and Physiography

The figure 2 illustrates how the rock typology varies from Proteriozoic to the quaternary or alluvial deposits within the region. The soil typology present in the region consists of mid hills, high hills, mountaneous and dry hills. These account for the 1100m to the 4400m MSL respectively. The most important part of all these typologies is the output in the form of mineral deposits along the Beas River from Solang to Kullu downstream (figure 2). This results in placer type mineral deposits found in most of the parts in the region illustrated through a section in figure 1.

**Figure 1. Section through Manali deposit area
(Author, 2018)**

Figure 3. Geology & Physiography of the Region
 (Author, 2018)

Figure 2. Mineral Deposit Zones along Beas River
 (Author, 2018)

2-2- Land use/Land cover Timeline

The land use /land cover changes of the region explain how the forest areas have decreased in the past four decades. The forest lands are slowly getting converted to grazing lands and agricultural fields. The agricultural fields have also been replaced by the horticulture fields in the past two decades majorly. This shift in farming practices has invited extensive use of pesticides as well as fertilizers which has also been a major cause of formation of barren lands in the region as it leads to the reduction of land fertility in the region. Therefore, the timeline maps are an important method to understand the changing land use and land cover of the region with respect to exchanging anthropogenic activities in the region due to the economic benefits of the people residing in this region.

Figure 4. The left image shows the land cover in 1972 while the right shows that of 1989 (Author, 2018)

Figure 5. The left image shows the land cover in 1998 while the right shows the same in 2005 (Author, 2018)

Figure 6. The left image shows the land cover in 2005-07 & the right one shows that in 2012-18 (Author, 2018)

3. Water

The Beas River is roughly 460 km long and originates from two sources, namely, Beas Kund (4060m ASL) and Beas Rishi (4350m ASL). The two streams meet at Palchan village, almost 10km North of Manali to form the river. The river has numerous tributaries that forms smaller valleys in the region. These tributaries include the solang nala, malasu, phojal, sanjoin and sarvari nalas on the right bank and alain nala, dhuangan nala and Pārbati River on the left banks. All the major tributaries of the Beas are perennial and snow-fed in nature.

Total share of Upper Beas Region (analysis):

Western area = 27% (380sq.m.)

Eastern area = 34% (500 sq.m.)

Streams and Lakes = 7%

Figure7 . Share of Area (Author, 2018)

Figure 8. Water resources and streams w.r.t. the flooding zones in the region (Author, 2018)

Figure 9. Altitude wise forest classification and configuration of ground (Author, 2018)

The study area has 7 order stream which shows that the network has developed through a long period of time and is well knitted. The State Water Policy (2013) states that, there should be promotion watershed management through extensive soil conservation, catchment-area treatment, preservation of forests, and increasing the forest cover and the construction of check-dams and trenching along with efforts to conserve the precipitation in the catchment area itself.

4. Forest

1-4- Forest Typology

The forest covers almost 50% of the region and this has decreased in the past four decades (refer maps in section (2)). The forest consists of 77 species of trees, 70 species of shrubs, 94 species of herbs, 15 species of climbers, 7 species of bamboo and grass 26 species of wild animals and 81 species of birds.

The following classification of forest is documented by the Forest Department of India (FDI), responsible for conservation, protection and management of forest lands:

- A. Reserved forest: associated with myths, considers the reigns of devtas in them that help protect the sacred groves.
- B. 1 Class Protected forest: it lies near the settlement, honeycomb with cultivation. It has excess pressure of fuel wood timber and minor forest produces. Deodar and Kail are prominent species in this type.

- C. 2 Class Protected forest: it lies after 1 Class protected forest, away from the habitation areas and lie at a higher elevation. They are prone to erosional hazards and Fir and Spruce are prominent in this type.
- D. Un-demarcated and 3 Class forest: these are open type forests found near settlements with high land values. They are mostly encroached by human activities.

Figure 10. Forest Range/ Forest Fire and respective trees in the region (Author, 2018)

2-4- Hazard and Dependency

The figure (11) shows the forest fire prone area, affected in the past. This has majorly caused loss to life as well as property. The two maps show a relation between the spatial hazard and its respective forest species that is majorly present in the most fragile areas.

The surrounding settlements are dependent on the forest lands for various purposes, some of which are obtained by sample surveys on-site. There are listed below:

- Grazing of cattle, sheep and goats
- Grass and leaves for fodder
- Manure
- Agriculture and domestic implements
- Fuel, wood, charcoal: some diseased tree given for free to make charcoal
- Minor forest produce: right holders are allowed to remove grass, roots, herbs, flowers, etc.

The forest resources generate revenue in a number of ways, some of which obtained by survey and records from the FDI are listed below:

- Auction of dry tree waste: by the Himachal Government
- Sale of Medicinal herbs
- Film shooting
- Revenue from pitching of trekking-tentage
- Grant for timber policy: levy of fine for misusing or exploiting the forest lands.

Figure 11. Section through Kullu forest area (top) and section through Manali forest area (bottom) (Author, 2018)

Figure 13. Interpretative Ecological Mapping of the Region (Top) and relative sections of Naggar Town (bottom left) and Manali Town (bottom right) (Author, 2018)

Figure 16. Build up plan Structure (Author, 2018)

The watershed analysis serves the following roles:

- Quality of life with respect to the watershed
- The geological history and the hydrological processes in the area
- Land and water use and management system within the watershed
- 'People, places and environment': it tells the relationship between humans and environment

Figure 14. Issues Analysis (Author, 2018)

“How much do you value the Natural Resources?”

The ecological dependencies in Lug valley is defined by the flowchart (2). It clearly states that the people understand the importance of their watershed and maintain its quality and quantity by preserving their traditional practices. Therefore, it preserves the land and soil quality in the Lug valley. Some of these practices include dependency on the naturally flowing streams and spring water for their daily purposes including drinking. It also includes the practice of organic farming and reusing the waste products.

Figure 15. Plan showing issues analysis of the Lug Valley area identified for interventions (Author, 2018)

7. Pilot Project for Sustainable Living

1-7- Vision and Importance

Vision: "Land and Water Resource Management for Sustainable Production"

Approach used for integrated watershed development program:

- Reforestation
- Lug valley watershed development (largest watershed in the region)
- Wasteland reclamation (converting barren/sterile wasteland into something that is fertile and suitable for habitation and cultivation)
- Agro-forestry (integration of trees with agricultural crops/livestock management simultaneously)

Watershed management program includes the process of implementing land use practices and water management practices such that it may improve the quality of life of the people living and other natural resources within the catchment areas. For this purpose the Rain Water Harvesting Potential of the Watershed (RWHPW) was calculated by the author by using the following formula:

$$Q = A (\text{sq.m.}) \times C \times \alpha$$

Where,

Q – RWHPW in cu.m.

A – Area of catchment in sq.m.

C – Runoff coefficient

α – Avg. annual rainfall in m.

Smallest watershed in the area = E = Minimum percolation rate of water

Largest watershed in the area = B = Maximum percolation rate of water

Watershed with the highest percolation capacity = W

Watershed with the lowest percolation capacity = K

Watershed management helps in controlling pollution water and other natural resources. Comprehensive planning of these resources within the entire watershed is critical to protect the health of the resources.

Figure 17. Sub-watersheds of Lug Valley area in the Region (Author, 2018)

Table 2 . RWHP of Sub-watershed of Lug Valley (Author,

Sub-watershed	Area (sq.m.)	Runoff coefficient (C)	Avg. annual rainfall (m)	RWHPW (cu.m.)
1	1000000	0.2	1.5	30000000
2	2000000	0.3	1.5	90000000
3	3000000	0.4	1.5	180000000
4	4000000	0.5	1.5	270000000
5	5000000	0.6	1.5	360000000
6	6000000	0.7	1.5	450000000
7	7000000	0.8	1.5	540000000
8	8000000	0.9	1.5	630000000
9	9000000	1.0	1.5	720000000
10	10000000	1.0	1.5	720000000

2-7- Policy Formulation

- Reuse rainwater in manmade storage points carved out of the natural slope and topography for irrigation and cattle rearing.
- Revive, regenerate and manage equity of existing springs in the watershed by improving its water quality and social management of the resource.

Table3 . RWHP of Lug Valley (Author, 2018)

WATERSHED	AREA (HA.)	RURHP (%)	RURHP (M ²)	RURHP (LITER/S)	PERCAPITA LITER/DAY
Forest/ Sub forests	7820684.56	0.1	1.4	11017973800	1888143.06.2
Savannah/ Grazing lands	84125428	0.2	1.4	8557622928	1418181.96.1
Agriculture/ Crop lands	58579472.1	0.25	1.4	11565988200	15781025.8
Barren/ Open land	7141484	0.1	1.4	1300815520	15781025.8
Roads/ Pavements	3300000	0.7	1.4	106000000	PERCOLLATION PATH
Rural settlements	873825.54	0.4	1.4	814315200	12.80071216
Urban settlements	871233.79	0.6	1.4	35338520	
TOTAL AREA OF LUG VALLEY WATERSHED				800000000	

Figure 18. Sub-shed (Author, 2018)

3-7- Proposal Details

Figure 19. (a) Proposed Plan for Bhaltha village (Author, 2018), (b) Area Plan (Author, 2018), (c) Detail Plan (Author, 2018), (d) Sample RWHP pits (Google, 2018), (e) Section 1-1, (f) Section 2-2

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